

Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V. (2014). Job satisfaction to job search – mediating role of intention to quit. HRM Perspectives: Insights on Human Resource Management Practices, June, 1-14, ISSN 2362-0900.

Job satisfaction to job search – mediating role of intention to quit

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Abstract

This paper investigates job satisfaction and its consequences of intention to quit and job search behaviour in a mediation model. The study was conducted in the telecommunication sector, which is one of the fastest growing business sectors of the country. Employees in the engineering job positions attached to these firms responded. The three-step procedure recommended by Baron and Kenny (1986) was used to test the mediation hypothesis. It was found that intention to quit fully mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and job search behaviour.

Key words: job satisfaction; job search behaviour; intention to quit

1. Introduction

The importance of employee attitudes beside capabilities and experiences for the effectiveness of organizations has been widely recognized. As a result, investigations on employee attitudes have become more prominent and periodic practice in organizations world over. Job satisfaction is such frequently studied attitudinal concept in several disciplines such as psychology, sociology, economics and management sciences since it has been identified as playing an important role in deciding subjective well-being of employees, and a predictor of employees' intentions (Price, 2001). For instance, employees' intentions of whether to work or not, what kind of job to accept or stay in, and how hard to work for the employer are all likely to depend in part upon the subjective evaluation of their work, in other words, their level of job satisfaction (Clark, 2001). Previous studies showed that an increase in job satisfaction results in improved job commitment and increased job performance (Price, 2001)

while less satisfaction with their jobs results in increased propensity for counterproductive behaviours, such as withdrawal, absenteeism, burnout, and work place aggression (Ellickson & Logsdon 2001).

Two undesirable consequences of job satisfaction are intention to quit and job search behaviour (Igarria & Guimaraes, 1993; Khatri et al., 2001; Sumner & Niederman, 2004). Several previous studies showed a strong relationship between job satisfaction and devotion to the organisation (Mathieu & Zajac, 1990), where less satisfied employees exhibit little loyalty to their organizations and may well be tempted to leave the organisation for anticipated higher rewards elsewhere. Hence, organizations today find difficulties in attracting and retaining employees (Khatri et al., 2001). This implies the importance of investigating employee's quitting intentions and their job search behaviours.

The present study investigates the relationship between job satisfaction, intention to quit and job search behaviour of employees holding engineering job positions in the telecommunication sector in Sri Lanka. The Sri Lankan telecommunication sector is considered to be one of the fast growing sectors in the South Asia. The expansion of business operations in this sector evidently require skilled, competent, knowledgeable and experienced workforce to outperform competitors. Yet, previous studies provide evidence that the telecommunication sector in Sri Lanka suffers from issues relating to employees' job satisfaction (Dissanayake, 2008; Fahim, 2012; Liyanaarachchi, 2011) and turnover (Algama, 2007). In the above context the specific objectives of this study were to investigate 1) the level of job satisfaction, intention to quit and job search behaviour of employees, 2) the relationships between job satisfaction, intention to quit and job search behaviour, and 3) whether intention to quit mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and job search behaviour. Consistent with the objectives, the rest of the paper reviews, in brief, the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and areas for future research.

2. Review of literature

2.1. Job satisfaction

The concept of job satisfaction has been widely studied over the last few decades in all parts of the world and as a result a plethora of definitions of this concept can be found in the literature. Table 1 provides highly cited such definitions of job satisfaction.

Table 1. Definitions of job satisfaction

Referenced work	Definition
Hoppcock (1935)	Any combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances that cause a person to say that he/she is satisfied with his/her job.
Brayfield and Rothe (1951)	How people feel about different jobs. The feelings range from highly satisfied to lowly satisfied.
Herzberg et al.(1967)	What does the worker want from his/her job
Lofquist and Dawis (1969)	Fulfillment of the requirements of an individual by the work environment.
Locke (1976)	A pleasurable or positive emotional state, resulting from the appraisal of one's job experiences.
Quinn and Staines (1979)	Affective reaction to the job.
Cranny et al. (1992)	Job satisfaction is a multidimensional construct that consists of overall job satisfaction as well as a variety of job satisfaction facets. Overall job satisfaction describes a person's overall affective reaction to a set of work and work-related factors.

Therefore, job satisfaction is a fairly complex multi-dimensional job-related attitudinal variable. It reveals an affective reaction to a job that results from a person's comparison of actual outcomes with those that are desired, anticipated or deserved. Job satisfaction is also considered as consisting of overall or general job satisfaction, which reflects one's overall feeling about the job, and a variety of job satisfaction facets, which reflect one's feeling toward different dimensions of work and work environment. Some of the most common and most important facets of job satisfaction are satisfaction with work content, pay, promotion, supervision, and co-workers (Igbaria & Guimaraes, 1993; Sumner & Niederman, 2004; Wickramasinghe, 2009).

2.2. Intention to quit

The turnover is the movement of employees across the boundary of an organization (Price, 1997). According to Price (2001), all most all research on turnover were focused on employees leaving rather than entering the organization. The terms "quit", "separation" and "intention to quit/leave" are used interchangeably to describe the turnover caused by an individual's own initiation whereas intention to stay is the extent to which employees plan to continue membership with the organization (Price, 2001). Mowday et al. (1982) found that employees with the intention to quit from the current organization subjectively assess whether they will be leaving the organization in the near future. Previous studies found that turnover intention and actual turnover are highly correlated and recommended to use intention to quit over actual

turnover because the data gathering of the latter is considerably difficult (Bluedorn, 1982; Price, 2001).

The cost of turnover includes the direct costs and indirect costs. Direct costs includes separation costs (such as severance pay and costs associated with an exit interview) and replacement costs (hiring, orientation and training costs). Indirect costs include costs such as loss of unit/department productivity due to lower productivity of the departing employee, loss in sales and customers resulting from the departing employee, and disruption to team dynamics of the unit/department. Therefore, the retention of employees has become a pressing need of any organisation.

Job satisfaction is identified as an immediate antecedent to intention to quit the workplace (Freeman, 1978; Rad & Yarmohammadian, 2006). Some previous research provide evidence that employees who experience higher levels of job satisfaction are more likely to be productive and stay on the job (Irvine & Evans, 1995; McNeese-Smith 1997) while some other previous research provide evidence that the probability of voluntarily turnover by employees decrease with higher levels of job satisfaction (Freeman, 1978). Overall, previous studies suggest a negative relationship between job satisfaction and intention to quit. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H1. Job satisfaction is negatively related to intention to quit.

2.3. Job search behaviour

The job search behaviour can be defined as the degree to which employees are looking for other jobs (Price, 2001). Job search behaviour can be explained using two alternative approaches, namely the intensity of job search and modes of job search (Ajzen, 1991; Blau, 1994). Intensity of job search describes the amount of time and effort individuals put in their job search behaviour (Ajzen, 1991; Blau, 1994). Formal modes of searching for jobs include private employment agencies, newspapers, journal advertisements, and internet whereas main informal modes include vacancy notifications through colleagues, friends and relatives (Blau, 1994).

The literature suggests that employees search for new jobs when they are not satisfied with their current jobs or when new job opportunities yield higher expected utility than their current jobs (Power & Aldag, 1985). It has long been understood that job changes for the individual employee usually involve searching for an alternative position or workplace outside the present workplace which, if successful, is followed by actual turnover (Mano-Negrin & Tzafir, 2004, p.442). Previous studies provide evidence for a strong negative

relationship between job satisfaction and turnover (Clark, 2001) and job satisfaction and intention to quit (Sousa-Poza & Henneberger, 2004). The literature also suggests that migration decision - i.e., moving from one place and settle in another, especially abroad- is an outcome of the job search behaviour (Baláz et al., 2004). Overall, these studies suggest, on the one hand, that job satisfaction and job search behaviour are related, and on the other hand, intention to quit and job search behaviour are related. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H2. Job satisfaction is negatively related to job search behaviour.

H3. Intention to quit is positively related to job search behaviour.

In addition, few previous studies suggest that the negative effect of job satisfaction on employee mobility runs through turnover intentions and job search behaviour (Böckerman & Ilmakunnas, 2004; Delfgaauw, 2007). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H4. Intention to quit mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and job search behaviour.

The conceptual model developed for the study is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

3. Methodology

3.1. Sample and method of data collection

Employees holding engineering job positions in the telecommunication firms in Sri Lanka were considered as the sample for the study. For the data collection, self-administered survey questionnaire was used. The questionnaire was pilot tested before distribution. A cover letter is attached to the questionnaire indicating the purpose and importance of the study, and ensuring confidentiality and anonymity of respondents to reduce self-report bias. A contact person was identified at each telecommunication firm to distribute the survey questionnaire

among randomly identified engineers in the engineering job positions. Preliminary investigations revealed that about 900 employees with engineering degrees hold engineering job positions in the telecommunication sector in Sri Lanka. 121 responses received, yielding a response rate of 57% of the original sample and covering 13% of the total study population.

With regard to demographics of the respondents, Figure 2 provides a better understanding of the distribution of age ($\bar{X}= 32$, $SD = 7.7$), tenure at the present workplace ($\bar{X}= 3.6$, $SD = 3$), and total tenure ($\bar{X}= 7.6$, $SD = 7.4$) of the respondents. 88% of the respondents were female. 52% of the respondents were married. 91% of the respondents had Bachelor's degree qualification, of those 90% obtained their Bachelor's degrees from the state universities.

Figure 2. Age and tenure distribution of respondents

3.2. Measures

Job satisfaction was measured by Porter and Lawler's (1968) single-item global measure of job satisfaction, which has been used extensively in the previous studies. According to Oshagbemi (1999), the single-item measure of overall job satisfaction is the most robust than multi-item scales. The item was on a seven point scale ranging from 1= not at all satisfied to 7=extremely satisfied, where a higher score reflected a higher level of job satisfaction. Intention to quit was measured by two-item scale of Meyer et al. (1993) this item was on a seven point scale ranging from 1=very unlikely to 7=very likely, where a higher score reflected a higher level of intention to quit. Job search behaviour was measured by the single-item scale of Blau (1994), which addressed the time spent on job search activities. This item was on a seven point scale ranging from 1=very seldom to 7=very often, where a higher score reflected a greater level of involvement in the job search.

3.3. Method of data analysis

For the data analysis, descriptive statistics, correlation and regression were used. The three-step procedure recommended by Baron and Kenny (1986) was used to test the mediation hypothesis. According to Baron and Kenny (1986), following conditions must be met to support a mediating relationship. First, the independent variable must be significantly associated with the dependent variable. Second, the independent variable must be significantly associated with the mediator. Finally, after the mediator is entered, the relationship between the independent and dependent variables should either disappear or significantly diminish.

4. Results

The level of job satisfaction, intention to quit and job search behaviour were analysed using descriptive statistics. On a 7-point scale, job satisfaction ($\bar{X} = 5.37$, $SD = 1.01$) and intention to quit ($\bar{X} = 4.56$, $SD = .97$) can be identified as moderate. Although job search behaviour can be identified as low ($\bar{X} = 3.57$, $SD = 2.16$), its standard deviation is considerably high. Figure 3 provides a better understanding of the nature of the distribution of job satisfaction, intention to quit and job search behaviour.

Figure 3. Job satisfaction, intention to quit and job search behaviour

To explain job search behaviour of individuals, a question was asked whether they searched for jobs within Sri Lanka or intended to migrate. The results showed that 57% of the respondents searched for jobs in foreign countries with the intention of migration, and the remaining 43% searched for better jobs within Sri Lanka.

Table 1 shows correlations between variables. Intention to quit and job search behaviour are significantly positively correlated. Job satisfaction is significantly negatively correlated with intention to quit and job search behaviour.

Table 1. Correlations

	1	2
1 Job satisfaction	1	-
2 Intention to quit	-.442**	1
3 Job search behaviour	-.329**	.476**

Table 2 shows the results of regression analysis. The results shows that job satisfaction significantly negatively predict intention to quit ($\beta = -.446$, $p < .000$) supporting H1. Job satisfaction significantly negatively predict job search behaviour ($\beta = -.333$, $p < .000$) supporting H2. Intention to quit significantly positively predict job search behaviour ($\beta = .470$, $p < .000$) supporting H3. After intention to quit is entered, the relationship between job satisfaction and job search behaviour disappear ($\beta = -.333$, $p < .000$ to $\beta = -.151$, $p > .10$), suggesting full mediation. Critical ratios of Sobel test, Aroian test, and Goodman test are also reported in Table 2. Accordingly, the mediation hypothesis (H4) that intention to quit mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and job search behaviour is supported by the data.

Table 2: Summarised results: regression analysis

Step	Variable	β	S.E.	R^2 (Adj.)
1	Job satisfaction \rightarrow Job search behaviour	-.333***	.192	.103***
2	Job satisfaction \rightarrow Intention to quit	-.446***	.132	.199***
3	Intention to quit \rightarrow Job search behaviour	.470***	.116	.220***
4	Intention to quit \rightarrow Job search behaviour	.409***	.129	.231***
	Job satisfaction \rightarrow Job search behaviour	-.151	.199	

Sobel test $t = -3.35$ ***

Aroian test $t = -3.32$ ***

Goodman test $t = -3.39$ ***

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

5. Conclusions and implications

The creation of an environment in which employees feel truly engaged or connected to the organization and its goals and objectives is vital to all organisations worldwide. Previous studies provide evidence that the telecommunication sector in Sri Lanka is suffering from high employee turnover rates and facing issues relating to employees' satisfaction with their jobs. In this context, this study was conducted to investigate relationships between job satisfaction and its consequences, in terms of intention to quit and job search behaviour. The identification of antecedents to and consequences of intention to quit have managerial implications in any country context.

The study investigated job satisfaction, intention to quit and job search behaviour of employees holding engineering job positions. Previous studies conducted on telecommunication sector suggest that engineering job positions in this sector were mainly occupied by highly qualified personnel (Algama, 2007; Fahim, 2012; Liyanaarachchi, 2011). The sample characteristics of the present study also support this view since 91% of the respondents had Bachelor's degree qualification, and of those 90% obtained their Bachelor's degrees from the state universities. The results of the study suggest that their level of job satisfaction is moderate. Yet, the results suggest that they had intentions of quitting the job and engaged in job search behaviour. Further, the results suggest that 57% of the respondents searched for jobs in foreign countries with the intention of migration while the remaining 43% searched for better job opportunities within Sri Lanka. In this regard, a departing engineer creates a great trouncing to the firm due to loss of intellectual capital leading to various tangible and intangible costs. This situation could become exacerbate when realising that these educated individuals leaving the country creating an undersized talented workforce in the labour market.

Therefore, it is worthy of studying whether these engineers intend to quit their jobs due to the nature of job content and work environment of the telecommunication firms, which impact on their job satisfaction. Previous studies such as Cranny et al. (1992) and Ellickson and Logsdon (2002) suggested the importance of work-related factors such as pay and fringe benefits, promotional opportunities, and relationship with supervisors influence employees' level of job satisfaction. In the Sri Lankan context, Liyanaarachchi (2011) found differences between job description and actual job tasks performed by engineers in the telecommunication sector. Therefore, future studies can extend the model proposed in this study by investigating antecedents to job satisfaction. Further, future studies can investigate different job search mechanisms used by individuals and the extent of time and effort devoted

in job search behaviour. With regard to the limitations of the study, a larger sample would increase the robustness of the findings. Further, although job satisfaction, intention to quit and job search behaviour are widely researched phenomena in the literature and can be generalizable, the findings on the intentions of migration may be influenced by factors beyond the telecommunication sector such as Sri Lankan and global political and socio-economic environment.

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